

Rapid determination of phosphate by indirect complexometric method

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In the present study, rapid determination of phosphate by indirect complexometric method has been reported by the precipitation of phosphate with excess lanthanum and titrating the excess in presence of precipitated phosphate without prior separation. Interference due to various cations and anions such as Al^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , F^- etc. have been overcome by using suitable masking agents.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Doubly distilled water was used throughout the experiments. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution (0.025 mol L^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water and diluted to 1 L. Lanthanum solution (0.025 mol L^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving $\text{LaCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water. EDTA solution (0.025 mol L^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving disodium salt of EDTA in water. Buffer solution pH 5.3 was prepared by dissolving sodium acetate in water and adjusting pH with acetic acid. Xylenol orange indicator, 0.1% (w/v) was prepared in water. A 1% (w/v) solution of 1,10-phenanthroline monohydrate was prepared in water.

Procedure :

To an aliquot of the stock solution containing 4.00 mg to 194 mg of phosphate was taken in a 250 ml conical flask. After neutralization, solution was maintained at pH 5.3 by adding buffer solution. An excess of measured volume of lanthanum solution was added to the mixture and the solution was heated to $70\text{--}80^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min. Solution was cooled and excess lanthanum was titrated with EDTA to a sharp color change of xylenol orange indicator from red to lemon yellow¹.

Results and discussion

In order to study the effect of pH on the precipitation of lanthanum phosphate, a series of experiments were done varying pH 3.0 to 8.0. It was found that pH 5.0 to 6.0 is suitable for quantitative precipitation of lanthanum phosphate. The precipitate of lanthanum phosphate at pH 5.0–6.0 was

colloidal in nature which hampered the titration of excess lanthanum. This problem had been solved by heating the solution at $70\text{--}80^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min and excess lanthanum was titrated with EDTA at pH 5–6 in presence of lanthanum phosphate precipitate using xylenol orange indicator. The determination of phosphate in sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution were performed and the results are given in Table 1. It has been found from the study that relative error did not exceed $\pm 0.19\%$ and standard deviation is $\leq 0.21 \text{ mg}$. On comparing the computed value of students 't' with the tabulated values (2.78 for 5% level of significance), it can be observed that in most cases there is no significant difference between the reference value and the values obtained by the present method. Al^{3+} and Zn^{2+} interfere with the determination of phosphate in the present method because of their cotitration along with lanthanum using EDTA. Interference due to Al^{3+} had been overcome by masking with acetylacetone at a temperature below 25°C . Interference from Zn^{2+} was removed by the addition of 1,10-phenanthroline. Among anions, fluoride ion interferes seriously with the present method of phosphate determination because of its strong complex formation with La^{III} , resulting in high values of the phosphate. The present method is applicable when sample contains fluoride up to 0.3 mg ml^{-1} . In case of high fluorine content, sample is required to be treated with HClO_4 and H_3BO_3 for the removal of fluorine.

Table 1. Determination of phosphate in sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution

Phosphate present (mg)	Phosphate found ^a (mg)	Relative error (%)	Standard deviation (mg)	Students 't' value ^b
3.87	3.87	0.00	± 0.02	0.00
7.74	7.75	+0.13	± 0.04	0.56
15.48	15.51	+0.19	± 0.07	0.96
38.70	38.65	-0.13	± 0.09	1.24
77.40	77.30	-0.13	± 0.15	1.49
154.80	154.69	-0.07	± 0.19	1.29
193.50	193.37	-0.09	± 0.21	1.38

^aAverage of five determinations, ^bStudents 't' at 5% level of significance = 2.78.

Note

Lanthanum to phosphate ratio in the precipitate, was determined by adding excess of lanthanum and titrating the excess with EDTA. From the amounts of lanthanum consumed due to precipitation of phosphate, the ratio of lanthanum to phosphate was found to be 1 : 1. The observed stoichiometry suggests that the compound formed in the precipitate is LaPO_4 .

Table 2. Analytical results for phosphate bearing materials

Sample	Concentration ^a (%)	RSD (%)
Phosphate glass	66.83 ± 0.04	0.06
Hydroxy apatite	42.07 ± 0.06	0.14
Hydroxy chloro apatite	30.04 ± 0.04	0.13
Superphosphate of lime	19.36 ± 0.04	0.21
Ammonium phosphate	53.39 ± 0.07	0.13
Bone ash	40.44 ± 0.06	0.15

^aMean ± SD (*n* = 5).

The method has been successfully applied to different phosphate bearing materials such as phosphate rock, phosphate glass, phosphatic fertilizer, hydroxy apatite etc. Solutions were prepared in acid taking 0.5 to 1.00 g of finely

powdered and dried (1 h at 105°C) samples. Phosphate was precipitated with a known excess of lanthanum(III) and determined by the procedure described earlier. The results are shown in Table 2.

This method is suitable for the determination of phosphate present in phosphate rock, phosphate glass, phosphatic fertilizer, hydroxy apatite etc. The method requires only 20–30 min for phosphate determination in sample solution. The additional advantage is to avoid filtration and maintenance of acid concentration and temperature during titration. The novelty of the method is its accuracy, rapidity and ease of operation.

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Reference

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